

SHORT NOTES

A Simple Derivation of Single-electrode and Redox Potential

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Every metal has a sufficiently large number of free electrons and ions of the metal. When a metal comes in contact with its solution, (i) some of the metal ions may come to the metal and react with the electrons, forming the metal atoms or (ii) some metal ions may pass to the solution, leaving the solid metal richer in electrons. In either case, the chemical reaction:

or its reverse will proceed till μ_e (chemical potential of 1g. equiv. of electrons) attains such a value that

$$\mu_{M^{z+}} + Z\mu_e = \mu_M \quad \dots (1)$$

Now μ_e is given by the equation :

$$\mu_e = \mu_e^\circ + N\epsilon E \quad \dots (2)$$

In equation (2) μ_e° is the chemical potential of 1g. equiv. of electrons in normal state, i.e., when the metal is not in contact with anything or when no electron or ion has gone of it or come to it; μ_e is the chemical potential when the potential of the solid metal as a whole is 'E' above that of the solution. In equation (2) ϵ is the charge carried by an electron and N is Avogadro's number. Since ϵ is negative, hence $N\epsilon = -F$, we can write the following equations:

$$\mu_{M^{z+}} = \mu_{M^{z+}}^\circ + RT \ln a_{M^{z+}} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\mu_M = \text{constant} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\mu_e = \mu_e^\circ - EF \quad \dots (5)$$

Substituting the value of '3', '4' and '5' in equation (1) we get

$$E = \frac{\mu_{M^{z+}}^\circ - \mu_M + Z\mu_e^\circ}{ZF} + \frac{RT}{ZF} \ln a_{M^{z+}} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{ZF} \ln a_{M^{z+}} \quad \dots (7)$$

In a redox potential system, we dip a noble metal in a solution containing an element in two stages of its valency, say Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} ions. Here (i) electrons will pass from the

noble metal and will reduce the ion having a higher positive charge or (ii) electrons will pass from the ion having a lower positive charge to the noble metal, thereby oxidising the ion. Either of the two processes will go on till the following equation is satisfied.

$$\mu_{\text{Fe}^{3+}} + \mu_e = \mu_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} \quad \dots (8)$$

Let us say that when equilibrium is established, the potential of the potential noble metal is ' E ' above that of the solution with which it is in contact. Substituting the relevant values in equation (8), we get the following:

$$\mu_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}^\circ + RT \ln a_{\text{Fe}^{3+}} + \mu_e^\circ - EF = \mu_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}^\circ + RT \ln a_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}$$

$$\text{or} \quad E = E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}}{a_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}} \quad \dots (9)$$

In a more complex system, governed by the equation:

the same reasoning will show that the redox potential will be given by

$$E = E_o + \frac{RT}{5F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{MnO}_4^-} a_{\text{H}^+}^8}{a_{\text{Mn}^{2+}}} \quad \dots (10)$$

If we measure the potential of the solution over the metal, as is usually done now, then single electrode potential will be given by the equation:

$$E = E_o' - \frac{RT}{ZF} \ln a_{\text{M}^{2+}} \quad \dots (11)$$

and redox potential by the equation:

$$E = E_o' - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}}{a_{\text{Fe}^{2+}}} \quad \dots (12)$$